

Thesis-1 Calculus in Binomial Expansion $(n) \rightarrow$ equation Using manual pattern Recognition

Binomial expansion has been a crucial calculation in mathematics for centuries, as it involves solving problems related to expanding 2 values $(a + b)$ with any power n . The current equation used for binomial expansion is:

$$(a + b)^n = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (a^{n-k}b^k) \quad (1)$$

However, in this thesis, I aim to propose an elegant, but less efficient version of the Binomial Theorem, which uses partial derivatives along with a factorial:

$$(a + b)^n = \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{1}{k!} \frac{\partial^k}{\partial a^k} (a^n b^k) \quad (2)$$

- where:
- a is the first term
- b is the second term
- n is the power of $a + b$

Deduction of the Equation

This equation was deduced from pattern recognition from the Pascal's triangle. Therefore, here are the first nine rows of Pascal's Triangle ($n = 0 \rightarrow n = 8$):

$$\begin{aligned}(a + b)^0 &= 1 \\(a + b)^1 &= a + b \\(a + b)^2 &= a^2 + 2ab + b^2 \\(a + b)^3 &= a^3 + 3a^2b + 3ab^2 + b^3 \\(a + b)^4 &= a^4 + 4a^3b + 6a^2b^2 + 4ab^3 + b^4 \\(a + b)^5 &= a^5 + 5a^4b + 10a^3b^2 + 10a^2b^3 + 5ab^4 + b^5 \\(a + b)^6 &= a^6 + 6a^5b + 15a^4b^2 + 20a^3b^3 + 15a^2b^4 + 6ab^5 + b^6 \\(a + b)^7 &= a^7 + 7a^6b + 21a^5b^2 + 35a^4b^3 + 35a^3b^4 + 21a^2b^5 + 7ab^6 + b^7 \\(a + b)^8 &= a^8 + 8a^7b + 28a^6b^2 + 56a^5b^3 + 70a^4b^4 + 56a^3b^5 + 28a^2b^6 + 8ab^7 + b^8\end{aligned}$$

As you may observe, a pattern between each term can be noticed, as n increases, similar to sequences. Therefore, infinitely many formulas can be generated for each term. For context and explanation, we will present each term in $(a + b)^n$ as:

$$(a + b)^n = \psi_1 + \psi_2 + \psi_3 + \psi_4 \dots \quad (3)$$

where: ψ_x is each term.

Before going into the proof, here are the equations that helped link patterns, generated from n th term sequences:

$$\psi_1 = a^n \quad (4)$$

$$\psi_2 = \frac{\partial}{\partial a} (a^n b) \quad (5)$$

$$\psi_3 = \frac{n(n-1)(a^{n-2}b^2)}{2} \quad (6)$$

$$\psi_4 = \frac{n(n-1)(n-2)(a^{n-3}b^3)}{6} \quad (7)$$

$$\psi_5 = \frac{n(n-1)(n-2)(n-3)(a^{n-4}b^4)}{24} \quad (8)$$

$$\psi_{n-1} = \frac{\partial}{\partial b} (ab^n) \quad (9)$$

$$\psi_n = b^n \quad (10)$$

Proof for $\frac{\partial}{\partial a} (a^n b)$

Let us observe the 2nd term of each $n \geq 2$:

$$2ab, 3a^2b, 4a^3b, 5a^4b, 6a^5b, 7a^6b, 8a^7b$$

The difference between the power of a , and its coefficient is 1, where the power is one less than the coefficient itself, but with the same power of 1. Secondly, the coefficient is the same as the n in $(a + b)^n$, with respect to Pascal's Triangle. Therefore, the 2nd term can be described as:

$$\psi_2 = na^{n-1}b \quad (11)$$

Which is the default expression used for finding the ψ_2 term in mathematics generally.

However, there is an interesting connection for the equation of ψ_2 with derivatives. By default, derivatives of an exponential function is described as:

$$\frac{d}{dx}(x^n) = nx^{n-1} \quad (12)$$

The equation used for ψ_2 is similar (11) to this, except b is left alone. Since one variable needs no change, but the other needs differentiation, we use partial derivatives to represent the expression as (14) instead of (13):

$$\psi_2 = b \cdot \frac{d}{da}(a^n) \quad (13)$$

$$\psi_2 = \frac{\partial}{\partial a}(a^n b) \quad (14)$$

Therefore we obtain the ψ_2 equation. The similar method can be used to find the second last term ψ_{n-1} , except the properties of a transfer to b .

Proof for $\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{1}{k!} \frac{\partial^k}{\partial a^k} (a^{n-k} b^k)$

We will begin by finding ψ_3 , using a similar approach to finding equation (11): pattern recognition. Extracting the ψ_3 term for each $n \geq 3$:

$$3ab^2, 6a^2b^2, 10a^3b^2, 15a^4b^2, 21a^5b^2, 28a^6b^2$$

Here, the difference between the coefficients of ψ_3 is similar to a quadratic sequence pattern:

$$3, 6, 10, 15, 21, 28$$

Using the expressions to find a, b, c in $ax^2 + bx + c = 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} 2a &= 1 \\ 3\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) + b &= 3 \Rightarrow a = \frac{1}{2}, b = \frac{3}{2}, c = 1 \\ \frac{1}{2} + \frac{3}{2} + c &= 3 \end{aligned}$$

Thus we obtain:

$$\text{coeff of } \psi_3 = \frac{1}{2}n^2 + \frac{3}{2}n + 1 \quad (15)$$

However, a problem arises when substituting the power n from $(a + b)^n$, as we obtain wrong results, compared to plugging in, say, $n = 1$:

Using power 3: $\frac{1}{2}(3)^2 + \frac{3}{2}(3) + 1 = 10 \neq 3$.

On the other hand, using $n = 1$, we obtain:

$$\text{power 1} = \frac{1}{2}(1)^2 + \frac{3}{2}(1) + 1 = 3 \equiv 3$$

When used for $n = 2$ instead of $n = 4$, and above $n \geq 3$, we notice the results obtained for $n - 2$ is equal to the coefficients of ψ_3 instead of using n or $n - 1$. Therefore, we write the difference as $n - 2$, instead of n :

$$\psi'_3 = \frac{1}{2}(n - 2)^2 + \frac{3}{2}(n - 2) + 1 \quad (16)$$

This equation can be simplified into:

$$\psi_3 = \frac{n(n - 1)}{2} \quad (17)$$

Unfortunately, the equation is not complete, as this equation only generates coefficients, not $a^n b^n$. Similar to finding (12), we use pattern recognition to find that the power of a is 2 less than n , and the power of b is similar to the constant 2 of a 's power, but positive. Combining this with equation (17), we obtain:

$$\psi_3 = \frac{n(n - 1)(a^{n-2}b^2)}{2} \quad (18)$$

Similarly, we can use the same method to find ψ_4, ψ_5 and so on:

$$\psi_4 = n(n - 1)(n - 2)(a^{n-3}b^3) / 6 \quad (19)$$

$$\psi_5 = n(n - 1)(n - 2)(n - 3)(a^{n-4}b^4) / 24 \quad (20)$$

However, the method is inefficient, as we have to calculate a formula for each term. Fortunately, an equation can be derived from which these terms are generated automatically. We begin with trying to represent the numerator and denominator as an expression or sequence. For example, since we are trying to make all ψ_n obtainable from partial derivatives, we

simplify $n(n-1)(n-2)\dots$ as $\frac{\partial^k(a^n)}{\partial a^k}$, each derivative repeated generating $n(n-1)(n-2)\dots$ and so on.

That leaves us with the denominator. From binomial expansion, we know that the denominator uses combinatorics, meaning a factorial denominator that gives different combinations possible for $(a+b)^n$ terms, which can be obtained from:

$$x_{n+1} = x_n(n+1), \quad x_0 = 1 \quad (21)$$

as the denominators always follow 2, 6, 24... and so on. Finally, the terms can be represented as:

$$(a+b)^n = \sum \psi_n \quad (22)$$

Meaning, using multiplication of $\frac{1}{k!}$ with $\frac{\partial^k}{\partial a^k}(a^n b^k)$, we finally obtain:

$$(a+b)^n = \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{1}{k!} \frac{\partial^k}{\partial a^k} (a^n b^k) \quad (23)$$

Using $n=4$ as an example:

$$\begin{aligned} (a+b)^4 &= \sum_{k=0}^4 \frac{1}{k!} \left(\frac{\partial^k}{\partial a^k} (a^n b^k) \right) \quad (1) \\ &= a^4 + 4a^3b + 6a^2b^2 + 4ab^3 + b^4 \end{aligned}$$

We can also combine the normal equation of binomial expansion with derivatives:

$$(a+b)^n = a^n + \frac{\partial}{\partial a} (a^n b) + \sum_{k=2}^{n-2} \binom{n}{k} (a^{n-k} b^k) \quad (2)$$

This helps us connect calculus with an unrelated combinatorics equation, making it elegant and a potential candidate for complex analysis.